

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

This issue (November 1999) is the last that appears in 1999 (the December issue will come out sometime in January as usual), so it is time for my sincere seasonal greetings, wishes and thanks! All the best, and please keep supporting J.UCS. And indeed, we have come to an important juncture and your help is needed:

J.UCS has been free of charge, so far. However, it was announced from the very beginning that eventually J.UCS will only be available for a charge. This is now taking effect starting with the January issue of the year 2000. Back issues are left open for the next few months so that authors and readers can get an impression of the journal, but even access to back issues will eventually be restricted to paying customers.

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Also, please do not forget to send us or solicit the sending of good contributions, will you? Thank you!

Yours cordially,

Hermann Maurer

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